

agro BRIDGES

**“Building bridges between consumers and producers
by supporting short food supply chains through a
systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”**

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

COORDINATION AND SUPPORT ACTION

“Let’s meet!” Event Validation Report

Responsible Partner: UNIMOS

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“Let’s meet!” Event Validation Report – Latvia

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Table of Contents

1.	INTRODUCTION	6
2.	“LET’S MEET!” EVENT ORGANISATION DETAILS	7
2.1	Concept selection and definition of activities (programme)	7
2.2	Location, Venue/Space selection and arrangements	7
2.3	Personnel involved in the organisation of the event.....	9
2.4	Event material.....	10
2.5	Engagement of contributors and collaborators.....	12
2.6	Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation	12
3.	EVENT IMPLEMENTATION AND OUTCOMES	13
3.1	Event implementation	13
3.2	Event participation.....	15
4.	EVENT VALIDATION.....	16
4.1.1	<i>Validation of event concept by participants.....</i>	<i>16</i>
4.1.2	<i>Validation of “Let’s meet!” guidelines and templates by the organising partner</i>	<i>17</i>
4.1.3	<i>Limitations and barriers of the organising partner</i>	<i>18</i>
4.1.4	<i>Suggestions for improvement of the concept and guidelines</i>	<i>18</i>
5.	CONCLUSIONS	18

List of figures

Figure 1: Local market “Āgenskalns market” – Left: outside, Right: inside.....	8
Figure 2: Local market “Āgenskalns market” – products	8
Figure 3: Local market “Āgenskalns market” – general view	9
Figure 4: Main visual (adapted for social media use).....	10
Figure 5: Invitation from UNIMOS Linkedin Profile	11
Figure 6: Invitation from UNIMOS Facebook Profile	11
Figure 7: “Let’s Meet” event in “Āgenskalns tirgus” – Table set up.....	14
Figure 8: “Let’s Meet” event Participants	15

List of tables

Table 1: Event programme	7
Table 2: Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event.....	9
Table 3: Event participation.....	15

1. Introduction

The present report summarises the activities of **UNIMOS for the organisation and validation of the Culinary Event “Let’s meet!” or “Tiekamies!” event in Latvia, Riga on March 12th, 2023**. This event is one of the four “Let’s meet!” event concepts designed in agroBRIDGES Task 3.4 for the local promotion of Short Food Supply Chains, locally produced food and involved market actors, namely (i) Producer Events, (ii) Culinary Events, (iii) Celebrate local heroes / SFSCs, and (iv) Open Days. The organisation, planning and implementation of the event was performed using the guidelines and templates designed by FBCD for each event concept to enable actors in the agri-food sector in replicating the events in their local agri-food ecosystems.

The present report outlines all steps taken for the design, planning and implementation of the regional event, as well as the outcomes and evaluation of the event by the participants and the organising agroBRIDGES partner, to produce suggestions for the improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool. The remainder of the report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2** – Describing the concept selection, design, organisation and implementation of the culinary event “Tiekamies!” event in Latvia, Riga.
- **Chapter 3** – Outlining the validation results for the events by participants and the value found in the “Let’s meet!” guidelines by the organising partners when creating and launching their event.
- **Chapter 4** – Concluding remarks for the event and suggestions for improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool.

2. “Let’s meet!” event organisation details

2.1 Concept selection and definition of activities (programme)

Table 1: Event programme

Title of activity	Short description	Date & Time (local)	Location
12th March 2023			
Welcome	Presentation of agroBRIDGES project and its goals	12:00 – 12:30	Āgenskalns Market (the largest and oldest market in the neighbourhood supporting Latvian producers and SFSC)
Food tasting, producers’ presentation	Degustation of local products new menu and meet producers during the degustation organised in collaboration with and hosted by Āgenskalns Market	12:30 – 13:00	
Discussion	Discussion on how to build SFSC in Latvia	13:00 – 13:30	
Networking	Networking among participants	13:30 – 14:00	

2.2 Location, Venue/Space selection and arrangements

The venue used for the organisation of the event was the “Āgenskalns market”, located in Riga. “Āgenskalns market” does not only represent a physical location, but a team of passionate professionals supporting the local SFSC and ecosystem by serving as a multifunctional food hub for sustainably produced and locally sourced food in the area of the local market.

“Āgenskalns market” serves as a recreational and educational space for visitors of different ages and social groups with the integration of a wide range of activities like community kitchen, Youth station, urban gardens, community stage etc.

Through common cooking and engagement of different social groups there is an exchange of knowledge and good practices with an emphasis on sustainability and local products, preservation of tradition, reduction of food waste, and healthy lifestyle thus contributing to behavioural changes in food consumption habits.

Figure 1: Local market “Āgenskalns market” – Left: outside, Right: inside

Figure 2: Local market “Āgenskalns market” – products

Figure 3: Local market “Āgenskalns market” – general view

2.3 Personnel involved in the organisation of the event

Table 2: Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event

Specialisation	Number of employees	Expected role	In-house / External	Estimated effort (person days)
Graphic designers	1	Development of promo material	In-house	1 person days
Catering	4	Food and drinks for guests	External	N/A
Local Speaker	1	Person introducing guests to the concept, products, producers and collecting feedback	External	N/A
Organisation	2	Setting all details. Event promotion.	In-house	2 person days

2.4 Event material

The event was promoted on UNIMOS social media channels. A Facebook event was created, and the event was promoted by the main organiser - "Āgenskalns market".

Figure 4: Main visual (adapted for social media use)

The main visual is a promotional poster for an event. On the left side, there is a vertical strip containing the UNIMOS alliance logo, the Āgenskalna Tīrģus logo (a stylized 'A' with '18 1931' inside), and a photograph of a traditional Latvian pie (piņķis) topped with jam. The right side of the poster features the 'agro BRIDGES' logo, the headline 'Tiekamies! Let's meet!', a heart-shaped logo with a ribbon, and the text 'LATVIJA'. Below this, it states the event's purpose: 'Tiekamies, lai nodegustētu vietējos pārtikas produktus, jaunas receptes un parunātu, kā atbalstīt īsās pārtikas piegādes ķēdes.' The event details are: 'Kulinārijas pasākums', '12.marts 2023', '12:00', and the location 'Āgenskalna tirgus, Nometņu iela 64, Rīga, Latvija'. The website 'www.agrobridges.eu' is listed at the bottom. A small European Union flag and a project reference number are also present.

UNIMOS
alliance

18 1931
ĀGENSKALNA TIRĢUS

agro
BRIDGES

Tiekamies!
Let's meet!

LATVIJA

Tiekamies, lai nodegustētu vietējos pārtikas produktus, jaunas receptes un parunātu, kā atbalstīt īsās pārtikas piegādes ķēdes.

Kulinārijas pasākums
12.marts 2023
12:00

Āgenskalna tirgus
Nometņu iela 64, Rīga, Latvija

www.agrobridges.eu

PrProjekts ir saņēmis ES pētniecības un inovāciju programmas "Apvārsnis 2020" finansējumu, pamatojoties uz dotācijas līgumu Nr. 101000788

Figure 5: [Invitation from UNIMOS LinkedIn Profile](#)

U. UNIMOS Alliance
318 followers
3w •

We would like to invite you to **AgroBridges Project 2021-2023 Let's Meet** event organised by **UNIMOS Alliance**, with help from our friends from Latvia. ...see more

[See translation](#)

UNIMOS
alliance

ĀGENSKALNA TIRGUS

agr
BRIDGES

Tiekamies!
Let's meet!

LATVIJA

Tiekamies, lai nodedūstētu vietējos pārtikas produktus, jaunas receptes un parunātu, kā atbalstīt šīs pārtikas piegādes ķēdes.

12.marts 2023
12:00

Āgenskalna tirgus
Nometņu iela 64, Rīga, Latvia

www.agrobridges.eu

Projekts ir saistīts ar iniciatīvu "Kvalitāte 2020" Finanšu atbalsta shēmas ietvaros. Nr. 33322/188

1

Like Comment

Figure 6: [Invitation from UNIMOS Facebook Profile](#)

U. Unimos utworzył(a) wydarzenie.
10 marca o 21:32 •

UNIMOS
alliance

ĀGENSKALNA TIRGUS

agr
BRIDGES

Tiekamies!
Let's meet!

LATVIJA

NIEDZ, 12 MAR
Vietējo produktu, jaunu receptu degustācija Āgenskalna tirgū
Ryga, Lotwa

[Wezme udział](#)

2.5 Engagement of contributors and collaborators

2-3 weeks before, potential local partners were identified based on their activity in the local SFSC ecosystem, accessibility and the venue - choosing the market “Āgenskalns tirgus” as a collaborator and a host was based on their activity and recognition among the local audiences. “Āgenskalns tirgus” has its own initiative twice a month inviting guests for “thematic Saturdays”, where they introduce new producers or products from specific regions. Moreover, the market is a nice place for the “Let's Meet” event as after the degustation guests can support producers by buying products directly from them.

2 weeks before, the restaurant was chosen based on the menu and support for the local SFSC - Nata Cafe is a small vegetarian and vegan cafe, shop and a producer of local vegan products created by vegetarian enthusiasts. Their dishes include a lot of vegan options, and they constantly experiment with new products and ingredients from local food startups.

Introducing vegan and sustainable menu options to consumers can be challenging due to numerous reasons like preferences of eating meat products and hesitation to try vegan alternatives, limited availability, cost and education, thus including vegan alternatives into the culinary event menu can help to start a conversation with consumers and introduce more local options to them.

The date and time were set, invitation was shared on social media, the event was created, information shared with the network.

1 week before the menu was confirmed with the cafe and the list of products was confirmed with the market representative who knows the producers and helped to buy, prepare products for the degustation.

2.6 Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation

Approximately 1 week before the social media event was created on LinkedIn, Facebook, social media posts were shared, invitations sent directly to the network and shared on collaboration partner social media (“Āgenskalns market” already had a great 20K followers). Additionally, the event took place at the well visited location during the market day, thus allowing more guests of the market join the event.

3. Event implementation and outcomes

3.1 Event implementation

To enrich our culinary event, different product options of local origin were included:

Types of food items that were served at the event were selected from the producers represented in the “Agenskalns market”, for example, a certified agronomist, fruit grower and apple breeder Eglons Brūns, who selects more than 500 apple varieties. Selection also included Burka & Ledus products from self-produced peppers in Latvia, Jelgava region - Ronalds Kreilis and Loreta Birzule have been masterfully producing a variety of sauces, pastes and pickled peppers for adherents of sharp flavours for more than a year now. Pepper is atypical vegetable in Latvia – while others grow tomatoes, cucumbers or paprika in their greenhouses, choice to grow pepper makes them unique. More products included cheeses, healthy fruit snacks from quince harvested and produced in Latvia by Nature Gift, organic beef smoked sausage by “Iecēnu delikateses”, bread by new family bakery in Riga Better Bread specialising in porous and crisp gluten-free bread, and new homemade pandan and hempseeds chocolate from Turbo Foods.

Vegan and sustainable menu options were chosen together with Nata Café, to educate visitors on new alternative products and recipes, including:

- čia kaviāra maizītes/ chia seed caviar snacks (product produced and sold by Nata Café)
- burkānlaša maizītes/ vegan carrot-lox mini sandwiches, a tasty plant-based alternative to traditional lox
- mini lēcu burgerītis/ mini lentil burgers
- zirņu bezpiena uzskoda ar marinētu “siļķes” baklažānu/ pea-based cottage cheese snacks with marinated eggplant
- saldīe bezpiena pončiki/ sweet pea based ponchiki (using products of local foodtech startup Got Foods,

Visitors were also invited to taste curd cheese & spreads, naturally fermented with probiotics inside tasty alternative to cream cheese, and Milk, dairy alternative produced from pure proteins found in split peas, produced by Latvian agrifood startup Got Foods. As well as, products from Latvian foodtech startup Fermentful were presented at the degustation. Fermentful produces 100% plant-based fermented drinks powered by green buckwheat to support mental and physical wellbeing. Both startups are Latvian rising food stars.

During the networking session, visitors were especially delighted about the Latvian foodtech startups and their tasty dairy alternative products. It appears that some of them had lactose intolerance and did not know that Latvian startups produce tasty alternatives as they are not yet on the shelves of large retail stores. Respondents also likely shared their excitement about “unusual” snacks from chia seed caviar, while mini lentil burgers were more popular with younger audience than meat producer options.

The highlight of the event was meeting producers themselves sharing a story of their products, especially apple breeder Eglons Brūns who is almost 80 years old and extremely passionate about selection and his produce. Visitors were following to his stand in the market and continued conversations event after the culinary event officially ended.

Figure 7: "Let's Meet" event in "Āgenskalns tirgus" – Table set up

3.2 Event participation

It was great to see so many people attend the event and participate in the activities. The event had a diverse group of participants, which made for interesting and engaging discussions. The market did a very good job of making it easy for people to attend and participate in the event, a suggested location in the market was well chosen. Taking into account that the event was organised on Saturday during the market day, we had a good turnout for the event. People attended the event by following personal invitations, event information on social media, yet the majority were just regular visitors of the market who got curious about the event. We received a lot of positive feedback from the participants, and many of them expressed interest in attending similar events in the future. Some of them suggested that similar events should be organised in different markets in Riga as well.

Figure 8: "Let's Meet" event Participants

Table 3: Event participation

Audience type	No. of participants
Producers	11
Consumers (based on consent forms)	59
Restaurant/ cafe	1
Total	71

4. Event Validation

4.1.1 Validation of event concept by participants

Question	Yes		No		Not sure	
Question #1: Were you familiar with the concept of Short Food Supply Chains before this event	23		34		2	
Question	Absolutely agree	Agree	Do not agree or disagree	Disagree	Fully Disagree	No answer
Question #2: Did you find this event informative about new/unknown types of food produced in your region?	37	19	2	1	0	0
Question #3: Did you find this event helpful for getting to know local food businesses, restaurants, their methods and efforts to bring local food closer to you?	30	27	2	0	0	0
Question #4: Did you find the activities organised helpful to understand the value of local food, local recipes and their various benefits for your health, the environment, and the society?	35	18	3	0	1	1
Question #5: Did you find enough information about how and where to find the local restaurants and kitchens and other hospitality businesses you've met?	32	14	12	1	0	0
Question	Monthly or more often	3-4 times a year	Twice a year	Once a year	Never	I prefer not to answer
Question #6: Would you like another similar event to be organised in your region? How often?	38	14	6	0	0	1

4.1.2 Validation of “Let’s meet!” guidelines and templates by the organising partner

Question #1: Did you find the event concepts relevant to your local agri-food ecosystem and organization?

In general, concepts are relevant, while different elements might be combined/ adjusted to the local ecosystem for the maximum value.

The event organising guidelines mostly focus on high-end or professional events that might not be relevant for all regions or smaller countries (top restaurants and high-end events are limited).

Toolbox targets farmers or food producers suggesting collaboration with restaurants and caterers, while the guidelines suggest the farmer or producers as event organisers. I believe that this is a rare scenario when a farmer would organise such an event in collaboration with caterers having a role of project manager, it might be more relevant to suggest ways/ materials helping the farmer/ producer highlight their presence or products at the event (e.g. how to present your product, major benefits of SFSC, how to tell your story in visual way or similar that helps project manager/ event organiser to promote farmer's products and tell his story).

Question #2: Would you organise the same event again in your region? If yes, would you make any adjustments?

Yes, as comes from the attendee feedback forms - vast majority of respondents would like similar events to be organised once a month or often. At least 3-4 times a year could make a significant difference in educating all - caterers, consumers, collaboration partners (e.g. markets) about the importance of SFSC and new products of local origin.

Question #3: Did you find the guidelines and templates sufficient for your event organisation needs?

General concepts were useful to set the direction - elements of the activity, programme and partners were identified based on local needs.

Question #4: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines accurate enough to plan effectively?

Guidelines for planning the events have sufficient principles for the event organiser/ project manager.

Question #5: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines flexible enough to create an event tailored to your ecosystem/business needs?

Guidelines for planning could be tailored for local needs.

4.1.3 Limitations and barriers of the organising partner

Choosing from a pool of local origin products, producers and farmers, opportunity for visitors to meet only few producers at the event due to their busy schedule or selling in the market by themselves (limited ability to leave the stand for the whole duration of the event).

4.1.4 Suggestions for improvement of the concept and guidelines

Question #5: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines flexible enough to create an event tailored to your ecosystem/business needs?

It might be worth considering including a few simple, easily understandable illustrations/ visual materials that explains the concept of SFSC and major benefits it presents for the farmers, environment and health that could be used at the event (in a form of banner, leaflet or other).

5. Conclusions

In general, guests liked the event. The date, time and the venue chosen was easily accessible and provided a meeting place for different audiences.

Positive aspects:

- More than third part of the audience (23 out of 59) knew the concept of SFSC before visiting the event
- The majority of attendees (56 out of 59) strongly agreed or agreed that this event provided them with information about new products/ previously unknown products of local origin
- The majority of attendees (57 out of 59) strongly agreed or agreed that this event was useful for them to learn about local food companies, caterers, their methods and efforts to bring local food closer to them
- The majority of attendees (53 out of 59) strongly agreed or agreed that such activities are useful for understanding the value of local food, local recipes and their positive impact on health, the environment and society and would like similar events to be organised more often (38 - once a month or more often, 14 - three or four times a year)
- The venue had dining tables where guests were able to sit, enjoy the products and fill in the questionnaire (alone or with the family members)

Room for improvement:

Following the respondent feedback, more information should be included on how and where to find the presented local producers and catering companies. While the majority found information provided to be sufficient, 12 out of 59 respondents highlighted that the information was sufficient, yet they have to search further themselves.

- The majority of attendees (34 out of 59) highlighted that they didn't know the concept of SFSC before this event
- Despite the majority (35 - totally agree) that this activity was useful for understanding the value of local food, local recipes and their positive impact on health, the environment and society, during the on-site conversations it was clear that this belief is mainly based on the assumption "local is good".

Recommendations:

1. More information should be included during the event on how and where to find the presented local producers and catering companies. This could be achieved by:
 - recruiting more people to present products during the degustation (communicate individually with visitors, get to know them and their needs)
 - inviting producers to the degustation to present their products themselves (and meet consumers to enhance recognition and build trust)
 - prepare visual materials for the menu/ catering company location/ producer location in the market (QR codes could be included that lead to more information about the product origin and buying opportunities)
2. In order to raise awareness about the SFSC concept the following additional activities might be considered:
 - visual material at the event explaining/ illustrating the concept of SFSC in a simple, easy understandable way
 - additional gamification elements used that helps to illustrate benefits (cause-result effect) of SFSC and their different models
3. Additional educational elements might be included to the event helping to highlight all the benefits provided by SFSC, especially how their choices impact the farmers/ local producers/ environment/ health and society in general - maybe also call attention to region specific local "superfoods" or ingredients.